

QCD tests with inclusive τ decays: the strong coupling

Antonio Pich *¹ and Antonio Rodríguez Sánchez ²

¹IFIC, Universitat de València – CSIC, Apt. Correus 22085, 46071 València, Spain

²Departamento de Física, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, 45004 Toledo, Spain

Abstract

The inclusive distribution of hadrons in τ decay provides a very precise determination of the strong coupling at low energies: $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2) = 0.320 \pm 0.012$. Evolved to the Z mass scale, it implies $\alpha_s(M_Z^2) = 0.1187 \pm 0.0015$. Complementary ways to test non-perturbative aspects of QCD with τ decay data are also discussed.

1 Introduction

The invariant-mass distribution of the final hadrons in τ decay measures the absorptive part of the W^\pm self-energy, $\text{Im}\Pi_{V+A}(s)$, in the kinematical range $s_{\text{th}} \leq s \leq m_\tau^2$, with s_{th} the hadronic mass-squared threshold [30, 31]. Considering only the Cabibbo-allowed decay width and neglecting the tiny effects from the up and down quark masses, the relevant dynamical quantities are the two-point functions

$$i \int d^4x e^{iqx} \langle 0 | T[\mathcal{J}^\mu(x) \mathcal{J}^{\nu\dagger}(0)] | 0 \rangle = (-g^{\mu\nu} q^2 + q^\mu q^\nu) \Pi_{\mathcal{J}}(q^2), \quad (1)$$

with \mathcal{J} the vector $V^\mu = \bar{u}\gamma^\mu d$ or axial-vector $A^\mu = \bar{u}\gamma^\mu\gamma_5 d$ colour-singlet charged currents.

For any weight function $\omega(s)$, analytic in $|s| \leq s_0$, the analyticity properties of the correlators $\Pi_{\mathcal{J}}(s)$ in the complex s plane imply the exact mathematical identity [14]

$$A_{\mathcal{J}}^\omega(s_0) \equiv \int_{s_{\text{th}}}^{s_0} \frac{ds}{s_0} \omega(s) \text{Im}\Pi_{\mathcal{J}}(s) = \frac{i}{2} \oint_{|s|=s_0} \frac{ds}{s_0} \omega(s) \Pi_{\mathcal{J}}(s), \quad (2)$$

where the complex integral in the right-hand side runs counter-clockwise around the circle $|s| = s_0$. The total inclusive τ hadronic width corresponds to $\mathcal{J} = V + A$ and $\omega_\tau(x) = (1-x)^2(1+2x)$ with $x = s/s_0$ and $s_0 = m_\tau^2$.

For $s_0 \leq m_\tau^2$ the left-hand-side integral in Eq. (2) is determined by the measured experimental distribution, while the right-hand-side can be theoretically computed as an expansion in inverse powers of s_0 , using the operator product expansion (OPE) [39]:

$$\Pi_{\mathcal{J}}^{\text{OPE}}(s) = \sum_D \frac{1}{(-s)^{D/2}} \sum_{\dim \mathcal{O}=D} C_{D,\mathcal{J}}(-s, \mu) \langle 0 | \mathcal{O}(\mu) | 0 \rangle \equiv \sum_D \frac{\mathcal{O}_{D,\mathcal{J}}}{(-s)^{D/2}}. \quad (3)$$

The first term ($D = 0$) contains the perturbative QCD contribution, which is known to $\mathcal{O}(\alpha_s^4)$ [3], while non-perturbative power corrections have $D \geq 4$. Taking the weight $\omega(x) = x^N$, the contour integral is only sensitive to non-perturbative corrections of dimension $D = 2N + 2$ (neglecting the small logarithmic dependence on s of $\mathcal{O}_{D,\mathcal{J}}$). For large-enough values of s_0 , the differences (quark-hadron duality violations) between the physical values of the integrated

*Presenting author.

moments $A_{\mathcal{J}}^{\omega}(s_0)$ and their OPE approximations are very small and can be efficiently minimized by taking “pinched” weight functions which vanish at $s = s_0$, suppressing in this way the contributions from the region near the real axis where the OPE is not valid [14, 23, 27].

The prominent $\rho(2\pi)$ and $a_1(3\pi)$ resonances get diluted by the opening of high-multiplicity hadronic thresholds, which results in a quite flat $V + A$ spectral distribution that approaches very fast the perturbative QCD predictions. At $s_0 \sim m_{\tau}^2$ the OPE can be safely applied. The weight $\omega_{\tau}(x)$ has a double zero at $s = s_0$, heavily suppressing the numerical impact of duality violations. The associated contour integral is only sensitive to OPE corrections with $D = 6$ and 8, which are strongly suppressed by the corresponding powers of m_{τ} . These power corrections have opposite signs in the vector and axial-vector correlators [14, 20, 33], enforcing an additional numerical cancellation in the total $V + A$ decay width. Thus, the non-perturbative contributions to the τ hadronic width are necessarily small, while the perturbative contribution amounts to a sizeable 20% effect because $\alpha_s(m_{\tau}^2) \sim 0.3$ is large. This observable is then very sensitive to the strong coupling [12–14, 29].

From a combined analysis of several moments, it is also possible to determine the non-perturbative contributions with experimental data [27]. The detailed analyses performed by the ALEPH [20, 37], CLEO [19] and OPAL [1] collaborations confirmed a long time ago the theoretical expectation [14] that power corrections are small.

2 Determination of $\alpha_s(m_{\tau}^2)$: 2025 status

The dominant uncertainty on the QCD analysis of the τ hadronic width originates from the unknown higher-order perturbative corrections to the correlator $\Pi_{\mathcal{J}}(s)$. The perturbative QCD contribution to the moment $A_{\mathcal{J}}^{\omega}(s_0)$ can be computed in two different ways: one can either expand the correlator $\Pi_{\mathcal{J}}(s)$ in powers of $\alpha_s(m_{\tau}^2)$ within the integrand (fixed-order perturbation theory, FOPT) [14] or perform the contour integral with a running $\alpha_s(-s)$, by solving numerically the five-loop β -function equation (contour-improved perturbation theory, CIPT) [28, 36]. Unfortunately, one observes a systematic difference between the corresponding results: CIPT generates a slightly smaller perturbative contribution and, therefore, a slightly larger fitted value of α_s than FOPT.

CIPT sums (known) large higher-order corrections generated by the long running of $\alpha_s(-s)$ along the contour integration, leading to a better perturbative convergence at low and intermediate perturbative orders [28]. However, it also destroys some renormalon cancellations that are preserved in FOPT [4, 5], which implies a worse behaviour at large perturbative orders. Modelling the large-order terms of the perturbative series with a few renormalons, it has been observed that the CIPT-FOPT difference remains at higher orders [7, 8, 21, 24–26] and some issues with a proper definition of the OPE condensates in CIPT have been pointed out. Recently, a gradient-flowed OPE without IR renormalons has been advocated [6], which agrees with the FOPT results, using lattice data to fix the regularized gradient-flowed gluon condensate. While the method still needs to be extended to $D \geq 6$, it clearly favours the FOPT approach.

Using the 2013 update of the ALEPH τ data [20], Ref. [33] performed an exhaustive re-analysis of the $\alpha_s(m_{\tau}^2)$ determination, both in CIPT and FOPT, exploring a large variety of methodologies in order to assess the systematic errors. The most reliable determinations of $\alpha_s(m_{\tau}^2)$ were extracted from the total $V + A$ distribution, as expected, while the separate analyses of the V and A spectral functions gave compatible values although with larger uncertainties. Table 1 summarizes the results obtained from the $V + A$ distribution with FOPT and different choices of pinched weights. The perturbative uncertainties were estimated varying the renormalization scale in the interval $\mu^2/(-s_0) \in (0.5, 2)$ and taking the range $K_5 = 275 \pm 400$ for the fifth-order coefficient of the Adler (logarithmic derivative of $\Pi_{\mathcal{J}}(s)$) series.

The weights $\omega_{kl}(x) = (1-x)^{2+k} x^l (1+2x)$ allow for a direct use of the measured distribution. Taking $(k, l) = (0, 0)$ and $(1, 0 \leq l \leq 3)$, one can fit $\alpha_s(m_{\tau}^2)$ and the power corrections $\mathcal{O}_{4,6,8}$. The

Table 1: FOPT determinations of $\alpha_s^{(n_f=3)}(m_\tau^2)$ from τ decay data, in the $V + A$ channel [33].

s_0	$s_0 = m_\tau^2$			s_0 dependence ($s_0 \geq 2 \text{ GeV}^2$)	
Weight	$\omega_{kl}(x)$	$\hat{\omega}_{kl}(x)$	$\omega^{(2,m)}(x)$	$\omega^{(2,m)}(x)$	$\omega_a^{(1,m)}(x)$
$\alpha_s^{(n_f=3)}(m_\tau^2)$	$0.319^{+0.017}_{-0.015}$	$0.319^{+0.013}_{-0.010}$	$0.317^{+0.015}_{-0.013}$	0.323 ± 0.012	$0.318^{+0.015}_{-0.012}$

variation of the results when \mathcal{O}_{10} is also included in the fit is taken as an additional uncertainty from neglected condensates of higher dimensions. One finds a high sensitivity to the strong coupling and a very small sensitivity to power corrections, which gets reflected in large errors for the fitted condensates. Additional power corrections with $D > 10$ would certainly modify the poorly determined values of the fitted condensates, specially those with higher dimensions, but their impact on α_s is expected to be smaller than the estimated errors. The extracted value of $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2)$ (second column in the table) agrees with the analogous ALEPH analysis in Ref. [20]. The minor numerical role of neglected higher-dimension condensates has been confirmed, repeating the analysis with modified weights $\hat{\omega}_{kl}(x) = (1-x)^{2+k} x^l$ which eliminate the highest- D power correction from every moment. As shown in the table (third column), one gets then the same value of α_s with a slightly smaller uncertainty.

Moments with the weights $\omega^{(2,m)}(x) = 1 - (m+2)x^{m+1} + (m+1)x^{m+2}$ are only sensitive to condensates with $D = 2(m+2)$ and $2(m+3)$. A fit to five moments with $1 \leq m \leq 5$ gives the result for α_s shown in the table (fourth column). A similar (and more accurate) value, $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2) = 0.319^{+0.010}_{-0.007}$ is obtained with the weights $\omega^{(n,0)}(x) = (1-x)^n$ ($0 \leq n \leq 3$), which have a very different sensitivity to power corrections; this result is not included in the table because the moments with $n = 0, 1$ are less protected against duality violations.

The minor role of non-perturbative effects at the scale m_τ can be also illustrated with a simple but very instructive exercise. If all non-perturbative contributions are neglected, α_s can be extracted from a single moment. Ref. [33] performed thirteen separate extractions of the strong coupling with the weights $\omega_0(x) = 1$, $\omega^{(1,m)}(x) = 1 - x^{m+1}$ and $\omega^{(2,m)}(x)$ ($0 \leq m \leq 5$). The first weight is very exposed to duality violations but power corrections are absent in the corresponding moment. Moments constructed with the second weight family are only sensitive to a single condensate $\mathcal{O}_{2(m+2)}$, while only $\mathcal{O}_{2(m+2)}$ and $\mathcal{O}_{2(m+3)}$ contribute with the third type of weights. In spite of the large disparity of neglected non-perturbative corrections, the thirteen determinations turn out to be in agreement with the results quoted in Table 1.

Fitting the s_0 dependence of a single $A^{(2,m)}(s_0)$ moment above some $\hat{s}_0 \geq 2.0 \text{ GeV}^2$, one can also extract the values of $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2)$, $\mathcal{O}_{2(m+2)}$ and $\mathcal{O}_{2(m+3)}$. This determination is more exposed to duality violations because the s_0 dependence of consecutive bins feels the local structure of the spectral function. The sensitivity to power corrections turns out to be very poor, but the extracted values of $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2)$ from fits with different \hat{s}_0 exhibit a surprising stability in the $V + A$ channel. Combining the results from the moments with $m = 0, 1, 2$, and adding the fluctuations with the number of fitted bins as an additional uncertainty, one gets the value of α_s quoted in the fifth column of Table 1. The agreement with the other determinations in the table confirms the very efficient suppression of duality violations in the doubly-pinched moments $A^{(2,m)}(s_0)$.

The weights $\omega_a^{(1,m)}(x) = (1-x^{m+1})e^{-ax}$ provide a completely different sensitivity to non-perturbative corrections. Since the high- s region is exponentially nullified, duality violations are very strongly suppressed, at the price of enhancing the exposition to power corrections of any dimensionality. A pure perturbative analysis should exhibit a strong dependence on s_0 and a of the fitted value of α_s , as a manifestation of the neglected power corrections. The amazing stability of the results obtained in a broad range of both s_0 and a clearly indicates that power corrections are small, for $s_0 \geq 2.0 \text{ GeV}^2$. The last determination in Table 1 shows the combined result from seven different moments ($0 \leq m \leq 6$).

Table 1 exhibits an excellent agreement among determinations with very different sensitivities to non-perturbative corrections. Together with the additional consistency tests successfully performed in Ref. [33], this demonstrates the robustness and reliability of the fitted values of the strong coupling. Averaging the five determinations in the table, one gets the final result

$$\alpha_s^{(n_f=3)}(m_\tau^2) = 0.320 \pm 0.012 \quad \longrightarrow \quad \alpha_s^{(n_f=5)}(M_Z^2) = 0.1187 \pm 0.0015. \quad (4)$$

This value is in very good agreement with the FOPT determinations of Refs. [2, 20].

3 Duality violations and the danger of ansatz assumptions

Instead of suppressing the unwanted violations of quark-hadron duality, Refs. [9, 10] maximize these effects, taking the weight $\omega_0(s) = 1$, in order to estimate them with some data points and, after extrapolation to the full range of s , subtract their contributions from the moment used to extract α_s . The OPE approximation to the integral in Eq. (2) is supplemented with the additional term [16–18, 22, 23]

$$\Delta A_{\mathcal{J}}^\omega(s_0) \equiv \frac{i}{2} \oint_{|s|=s_0} \frac{ds}{s_0} \omega(s) \left\{ \Pi_{\mathcal{J}}(s) - \Pi_{\mathcal{J}}^{\text{OPE}}(s) \right\} = -\pi \int_{s_0}^{\infty} \frac{ds}{s_0} \omega(s) \Delta \rho_{\mathcal{J}}^{\text{DV}}(s), \quad (5)$$

with $\Delta \rho_{\mathcal{J}}^{\text{DV}}(s) \equiv \frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im}[\Pi_{\mathcal{J}}(s) - \Pi_{\mathcal{J}}^{\text{OPE}}(s)]$ the difference between the physical spectral function and its OPE representation. Since a theory of duality violations (DV) does not exist, one needs to assume that the functional ansatz

$$\Delta \rho_{\mathcal{J}}^{\text{DV}}(s) = \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{J}}(s) e^{-(\delta_{\mathcal{J}} + \gamma_{\mathcal{J}} s)} \sin(\alpha_{\mathcal{J}} + \beta_{\mathcal{J}} s), \quad s > \hat{s}_0. \quad (6)$$

provides a reasonable description of $\Delta \rho_{\mathcal{J}}^{\text{DV}}(s)$ above some invariant mass \hat{s}_0 . The default choice $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{J}}(s) = 1$, adopted in [9, 10], describes the high-energy fall-off of duality violations through an oscillatory function with a damping exponential [38]. Refs. [33–35] introduced the modulation factor $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{J}}(s)$ to study the systematic uncertainties associated with this assumption.

The s_0 dependence of $A_{\mathcal{J}}^{\omega_0}(s_0)$ is fitted to the experimental distribution in $\hat{s}_0 \leq s_0 \leq m_\tau^2$, bin by bin, which is equivalent to a direct fit of the spectral function; the large number of unknown parameters require enough energy bins to be fitted, enforcing the choice $\sqrt{\hat{s}_0} \sim 1.2$ GeV. Once the ansatz has been fixed, the resulting model is used to compute $\Delta A_{\mathcal{J}}^\omega(s_0)$ and correct the perturbative prediction of the moments, for any $\omega(x)$: $A_{\mathcal{J}}^\omega(s_0)_{\text{pert}} = A_{\mathcal{J}}^\omega(s_0)_{\text{exp}} - \Delta A_{\mathcal{J}}^\omega(s_0)$. Since the higher-energy bins are used to fix the ansatz parameters, the main sensitivity to the strong coupling is achieved at the low scale \hat{s}_0 , where perturbation theory is suspect (some additional sensitivity is recovered varying $\sqrt{\hat{s}_0}$ between 1.2 and 1.38 GeV in a global fit). Thus, α_s is mainly extracted from $A_{\mathcal{J}}^{\omega_0}(\hat{s}_0)_{\text{pert}}$ and, taking additional weights $\omega(x)$, the power corrections \mathcal{O}_D are estimated from $A_{\mathcal{J}}^\omega(\hat{s}_0)_{\text{pert}}$.

The dangers of this prescription are quite obvious, since the achievable precision can never be better than the reached control on $\Delta \rho_{\mathcal{J}}^{\text{DV}}(s)$. Detailed analyses performed with different choices of $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{J}}(s)$ have revealed the following facts [33–35]:

1. The strong coupling is mainly fixed at a very low scale \hat{s}_0 , where errors are large and the subtracted duality-violation contribution is large and model dependent. Slight changes on the functional form of the assumed ansatz result in large variations of the fitted value of α_s . In fact, for any reasonable input choice of $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2)$, one can find ansatzes that fit the data even better than the default one.
2. Minor modifications of the ansatz can change the extracted condensates by several orders of magnitude because, once α_s and the ansatz parameters have been fitted, the power corrections need to be adjusted to compensate a slightly incorrect value of α_s plus the model-dependent duality-violation deformations.

3. Using pinched weights, the subtraction $\Delta A_{\mathcal{J}}^\omega(s_0)$ turns out to be negligible at $s_0 \sim m_\tau^2$, for all analysed ansätze. This confirms the efficient suppression of duality violations in pinched moments at the m_τ scale, refuting the original motivation of the duality-violation approach to α_s .
4. Those ansätze enforcing low values of α_s , like the default one in [9, 10], exhibit pathologies such as huge power corrections and unphysical behaviours outside the fitted region. On the other side, non-pathological scenarios give condensates of the expected size and values of $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2)$ within the 1σ interval of the determination in Eq. (4).

4 Testing nonperturbative QCD with τ decay data

The determination of $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2)$ from τ decay has a poor sensitivity to power corrections because the size of these small contributions is masked by the larger perturbative uncertainties. However, since the perturbative contribution cancels exactly in the difference between the vector and axial-vector correlators, quite precise non-perturbative information has been already extracted from the $V - A$ spectral function [22, 23].

The recent accurate determination of the strong coupling, $\alpha_s^{(n_f=5)}(M_Z^2) = 0.11873 \pm 0.00056$, by the ALPHA lattice collaboration [15], provides an opportunity to increase the sensitivity to non-perturbative corrections in the $V + A$ channel. While it is in excellent agreement with the τ determination in Eq. (4), the lattice value of α_s is three times more precise and completely independent of the τ decay data. We can then use the lattice information on α_s as an input to fix the perturbative contribution to the moments $A_{\mathcal{J}}^\omega(s_0)$. The pinched moments with weights $\omega_n(x) = 1 - x^n$ ($n \geq 1$) allow then for a direct extraction of $\mathcal{O}_{2(n+1)}$. Some preliminary results obtained with this strategy are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 [32].

The left plot in Fig. 1 shows the s_0 dependence of the moment $A_{V+A}^{\omega_0}(s_0)$ with the trivial weight $\omega_0(x) = 1$, which does not receive any power correction. The shaded region displays the perturbative prediction, using the lattice value of α_s , while the data points indicate the experimental evaluation. The excellent agreement between the two determinations persists at rather low values of s_0 , where the perturbative prediction deteriorates. In spite of not being protected by any pinch, this moment does not exhibit any signals of duality violations. For illustration, the red curve displays the perturbative prediction obtained with $\alpha_s^{(n_f=5)}(M_Z^2) = 0.1159$, the central value advocated in Ref. [9].

Figure 1: Left: predictions for $A_{V+A}^{\omega_0}(s_0)$ (shaded band), using as input the lattice value of α_s , compared to the experimental evaluation (crosses). The red curve shows the prediction for a lower value of $\alpha_s^{(n_f=5)}(M_Z^2) = 0.1159$. Right: $D = 4$ condensate extracted from $A_{V+A}^{\omega_1}(s_0)$ [32].

Using the weight $\omega_1(x)$, one determines the $D = 4$ condensate. The result, shown in the right plot of Fig. 1, remains very stable in a broad range of s_0 values. The large errors manifest

a poor sensitivity to the gluon condensate, as expected, since it is highly correlated with the perturbative uncertainties.

The three panels in Fig. 2 show, as functions of s_0 , the determinations of $\mathcal{O}_{6,V+A}$ (left), $\mathcal{O}_{8,V+A}$ (center) and $\mathcal{O}_{10,V+A}$ (right), using the weights $\omega_n(x)$ with $n = 2, 3$ and 4, respectively. The three results exhibit a very good stability with respect to s_0 , remaining always within the ranges estimated in Ref. [33]. The blue horizontal line in the left plot displays the large- N_C prediction, which looks smaller but not incompatible with the fitted value. The red horizontal lines in the three panels indicate the condensate values advocated in [11], which are clearly excluded by the τ data: they are far too large and have the wrong sign.

Figure 2: Values of $\mathcal{O}_{D,V+A}$ with $D = 6$ (left), 8 (center) and 10 (right), extracted from τ decay data, using the lattice determination of α_s [32].

A more detailed analysis of non-perturbative effects, combining the τ data with lattice information, will appear soon [32].

5 Summary

The τ data provides a wonderful laboratory to test QCD at low energies. The inclusive hadronic τ decay width is governed by the two-point correlators of the vector and axial-vector quark currents, which can be theoretically analysed with rigorous short-distance methods at the scale m_τ . The total Cabibbo-allowed decay width ($V + A$) is ideally suited to perform a clean low-energy determination of the strong coupling. It is completely dominated by the perturbative contribution and the small non-perturbative corrections can be controlled through analyses of the hadronic distribution.

An accurate determination of $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2)$ requires minimizing the uncontrollable violations of quark-hadron duality. To achieve this, one must use inclusive moments of the hadronic distribution, weighted with pinched factors (with low values of n) and s_0 large enough to profit from the exponential suppression of duality violations. From current data, one extracts the FOPT determination in Eq. (4), which has a 3.8% (1.3%) precision at the m_τ (M_Z) scale.

Combining the τ data with lattice information on α_s , one can increase the sensitivity to interesting non-perturbative effects. The preliminary results obtained so far indicate power corrections of the expected size. Further analyses in this direction are on-going.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank the organizers for making possible this lively and successful workshop. This work is supported by the Spanish Government and ERDF/EU (Agencia Estatal de Investigación MCIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033), Grants No. PID2023-146220NB-I00 and CEX2023-001292-S.

References

- [1] K. Akerstaff et al. Measurement of the strong coupling constant α_s and the vector and axial vector spectral functions in hadronic tau decays. *Eur. Phys. J. C*, 7:571–593, 1999.
- [2] Cesar Ayala, Gorazd Cvetic, and Diego Teca. Borel–Laplace sum rules with τ decay data, using OPE with improved anomalous dimensions. *J. Phys. G*, 50(4):045004, 2023.
- [3] P. A. Baikov, K. G. Chetyrkin, and Johann H. Kuhn. Order α_s^4 QCD Corrections to Z and tau Decays. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 101:012002, 2008.
- [4] Martin Beneke, Diogo Boito, and Matthias Jamin. Perturbative expansion of τ hadronic spectral function moments and α_s extractions. *JHEP*, 01:125, 2013.
- [5] Martin Beneke and Matthias Jamin. α_s and the tau hadronic width: fixed-order, contour-improved and higher-order perturbation theory. *JHEP*, 09:044, 2008.
- [6] Martin Beneke and Hiromasa Takaura. Gradient-flowed operator product expansion without IR renormalons. arXiv:2510.12193, 2025.
- [7] Miguel A. Benitez-Rathgeb, Diogo Boito, Andre H. Hoang, and Matthias Jamin. Reconciling the contour-improved and fixed-order approaches for τ hadronic spectral moments. Part I. Renormalon-free gluon condensate scheme. *JHEP*, 07:016, 2022.
- [8] Miguel A. Benitez-Rathgeb, Diogo Boito, André H. Hoang, and Matthias Jamin. Reconciling the contour-improved and fixed-order approaches for τ hadronic spectral moments. Part II. Renormalon norm and application in α_s determinations. *JHEP*, 09:223, 2022.
- [9] Diogo Boito, Aaron Eiben, Maarten Golterman, Kim Maltman, Lucas M. Mansur, and Santiago Peris. Strong coupling from hadronic τ -decay data including $\tau \rightarrow \pi^- \pi^0 \nu_\tau$ from Belle. *Phys. Rev. D*, 111(7):074010, 2025.
- [10] Diogo Boito, Maarten Golterman, Kim Maltman, James Osborne, and Santiago Peris. Strong coupling from the revised ALEPH data for hadronic τ decays. *Phys. Rev. D*, 91(3):034003, 2015.
- [11] Diogo Boito, Maarten Golterman, Kim Maltman, and Santiago Peris. Strong coupling from hadronic τ decays: A critical appraisal. *Phys. Rev. D*, 95(3):034024, 2017.
- [12] Eric Braaten. QCD Predictions for the Decay of the tau Lepton. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 60:1606–1609, 1988.
- [13] Eric Braaten. The Perturbative QCD Corrections to the Ratio R for tau Decay. *Phys. Rev.*, D39:1458, 1989.
- [14] Eric Braaten, Stephan Narison, and Antonio Pich. QCD analysis of the tau hadronic width. *Nucl. Phys.*, B373:581–612, 1992.
- [15] Mattia Dalla Brida, Roman Höllwieser, Francesco Knechtli, Tomasz Korzec, Alberto Ramos, Stefan Sint, and Rainer Sommer. The strength of the interaction between quarks and gluons. arXiv:2501.06633, 2025.
- [16] Oscar Cata, Maarten Golterman, and Santi Peris. Unraveling duality violations in hadronic tau decays. *Phys. Rev. D*, 77:093006, 2008.
- [17] Oscar Cata, Maarten Golterman, and Santiago Peris. Possible duality violations in tau decay and their impact on the determination of alpha(s). *Phys. Rev. D*, 79:053002, 2009.

- [18] Boris Chibisov, R. David Dikeman, Mikhail A. Shifman, and N. Uraltsev. Operator product expansion, heavy quarks, QCD duality and its violations. *Int. J. Mod. Phys. A*, 12:2075–2133, 1997.
- [19] T. Coan et al. Measurement of alpha-s from tau decays. *Phys. Lett. B*, 356:580–588, 1995.
- [20] Michel Davier, Andreas Höcker, Bogdan Malaescu, Chang-Zheng Yuan, and Zhiqing Zhang. Update of the ALEPH non-strange spectral functions from hadronic τ decays. *Eur. Phys. J.*, C74(3):2803, 2014.
- [21] Maarten Golterman, Kim Maltman, and Santiago Peris. Difference between fixed-order and contour-improved perturbation theory. *Phys. Rev. D*, 108(1):014007, 2023.
- [22] Martin Gonzalez-Alonso, Antonio Pich, and Joaquim Prades. Violation of Quark-Hadron Duality and Spectral Chiral Moments in QCD. *Phys. Rev. D*, 81:074007, 2010.
- [23] Martín González-Alonso, Antonio Pich, and Antonio Rodríguez-Sánchez. Updated determination of chiral couplings and vacuum condensates from hadronic τ decay data. *Phys. Rev. D*, 94(1):014017, 2016.
- [24] Néstor G. Gracia, André H. Hoang, and Vicent Mateu. Mathematical aspects of the asymptotic expansion in contour improved perturbation theory for hadronic tau decays. *Phys. Rev. D*, 108(3):034013, 2023.
- [25] André H. Hoang and Christoph Regner. On the difference between FOPT and CIPT for hadronic tau decays. *Eur. Phys. J. ST*, 230(12-13):2625–2639, 2021.
- [26] André H. Hoang and Christoph Regner. Borel representation of τ hadronic spectral function moments in contour-improved perturbation theory. *Phys. Rev. D*, 105(9):096023, 2022.
- [27] François Le Diberder and Antonio Pich. Testing QCD with tau decays. *Phys. Lett.*, B289:165–175, 1992.
- [28] François Le Diberder and Antonio Pich. The perturbative QCD prediction to R_τ revisited. *Phys. Lett.*, B286:147–152, 1992.
- [29] Stephan Narison and Antonio Pich. QCD Formulation of the tau Decay and Determination of Λ_{MS} . *Phys. Lett.*, B211:183–188, 1988.
- [30] Antonio Pich. Precision Tau Physics. *Prog. Part. Nucl. Phys.*, 75:41–85, 2014.
- [31] Antonio Pich. Precision physics with inclusive QCD processes. *Prog. Part. Nucl. Phys.*, 117:103846, 2021.
- [32] Antonio Pich and Antonio Rodríguez-Sánchez. To appear.
- [33] Antonio Pich and Antonio Rodríguez-Sánchez. Determination of the QCD coupling from ALEPH τ decay data. *Phys. Rev. D*, 94(3):034027, 2016.
- [34] Antonio Pich and Antonio Rodríguez-Sánchez. Updated determination of $\alpha_s(m_\tau^2)$ from tau decays. *Mod. Phys. Lett. A*, 31(30):1630032, 2016.
- [35] Antonio Pich and Antonio Rodríguez-Sánchez. Violations of quark-hadron duality in low-energy determinations of α_s . *JHEP*, 07:145, 2022.
- [36] A. A. Pivovarov. Renormalization group analysis of the tau lepton decay within QCD. *Z. Phys.*, C53:461–464, 1992. [*Yad. Fiz.*54,1114(1991)].

- [37] S. Schael et al. Branching ratios and spectral functions of tau decays: Final ALEPH measurements and physics implications. *Phys. Rept.*, 421:191–284, 2005.
- [38] Mikhail A. Shifman. Quark hadron duality. In *8th International Symposium on Heavy Flavor Physics*, volume 3, pages 1447–1494, Singapore, 7 2000. World Scientific.
- [39] Mikhail A. Shifman, A. I. Vainshtein, and Valentin I. Zakharov. QCD and Resonance Physics. Theoretical Foundations. *Nucl. Phys. B*, 147:385–447, 1979.